
Effect of Selected Yogic Practices on Two Hand Coordination and Wellbeing of Male Inter-Collegiate Level Sportsperson

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the impact of selected yogic practices on two-hand coordination and wellbeing of male sportspersons participating in inter-collegiate competitions under Kuvempu University. Forty male athletes (n=40) were randomly divided into an experimental group (n=20) and a control group (n=20). The experimental group underwent yoga training three days a week (Monday, Wednesday, and Friday) for twelve weeks, while the control group continued with their regular routines without any yoga intervention. The yoga regimen included 48 asanas, Pranayama, Surya Namaskar, and meditation, selected in consultation with experts. Two hand Coordination and wellbeing were measured using standardized tests. Descriptive statistics and paired sample *t*-tests were used to analyze the data, with significance set at 0.05. Results showed significant improvement in the experimental group's two-hand coordination and wellbeing from pre- to post-test, while the control group showed no notable changes. The findings suggest that regular yogic practices positively influence two hand coordination and overall wellbeing in athletes.

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INTRODUCTION

Yoga, an ancient discipline from India, is one of the oldest systems of personal development, integrating the body, mind, and spirit. Through structured postures (asanas), it enhances physical strength, flexibility, and mental clarity. Regular practice stimulates key bodily systems, including circulation, digestion, respiration, and the nervous and endocrine systems, promoting overall health and vitality (Sahu D P., 2019).

Yoga for Sportspersons

Yoga is a holistic practice that enhances physical strength, mental clarity, and energy levels, making it especially beneficial for athletes. It supports lung function, improves flexibility, muscle coordination, and focus, while also promoting mental well-being by reducing stress and boosting confidence. Yoga encourages a balanced connection between mind and body, helping athletes perform better both physically and mentally (Hanamanhappa & Prasannakumar, 2023). Yoga supports athletes by enhancing physical, mental, emotional, and energy levels. Practices like Asanas, Pranayama, Kriyas, and Mudras improve body systems such as cardiovascular, respiratory, digestive, and nervous systems. Mentally, yoga reduces stress, anxiety, and negative emotions, promoting focus and emotional balance. It also increases motivation, reduces fatigue, and strengthens inner resilience. By removing mental blocks and improving overall well-being, yoga plays a key role in boosting athletic performance (Tripathy, P., & Nayak, P. 2022).

Two hand Coordination in Sportspersons

Hand-eye coordination is a key skill in many sports, directly affecting performance. It involves the precise control of hand and finger movements through the integration of sensory input and motor control (Giles et al., 2020). Activities such as juggling, playing catch, ping-pong, rope jumping, and martial arts can help enhance this ability. Training should involve both hands, consistent practice, and varied exercises for better results (Stubbs et al., 2017). Developing hand coordination supports sport-specific actions like shooting, catching, or swinging, and requires focus on dexterity, grip strength, and fine motor skills (HM Government, 2011). Continuous practice and tailored routines lead to gradual improvement.

Athletes' Mental Well-being

Mental health is a serious issue that affects many people around the world (Olesen et al., 2012; Schuch et al., 2016). Problems like stress, anxiety, tiredness, sleep issues, and headaches are common signs. Mental health includes many conditions, from mild to severe. Studies show that regular physical activity can improve mental health. It can help reduce depression and anxiety, even in people with brain-

related conditions (Adamson et al., 2015; Schuch et al., 2016). Exercise also helps people feel better, manage stress, and improve their confidence and social skills (Stubbs et al., 2017). For athletes, keeping good mental health is important. It helps them perform better, stay motivated, and enjoy their sport. That's why it's important to support and check on athletes' mental well-being regularly.

Enhancing Two-Hand Coordination and Wellbeing in Sportspersons through Yoga

Yoga has emerged as an effective tool for improving two-hand coordination and overall wellbeing among sportspersons. Through the practice of specific asanas, pranayama techniques, and mindfulness exercises, athletes can develop better bilateral motor skills and enhance mental resilience. Postures such as *Vrikshasana* (Tree Pose) and *Padmasana* (Lotus Pose) involve balanced, controlled movements that activate both hemispheres of the brain, promoting improved hand coordination (Telles, Singh, & Balkrishna, 2012). Similarly, dynamic sequences like *Surya Namaskar* (Sun Salutation) integrate rhythmic, bilateral actions that refine neuromuscular synchronization. Breathing exercises such as *Nadi Shodhana* (alternate nostril breathing) and *Bhramari* (humming bee breath) contribute to calming the autonomic nervous system, enhancing focus, and reducing performance anxiety (Streeter et al., 2012). Regular engagement with yoga has also been shown to lower cortisol levels, helping athletes manage stress more effectively and sustain higher levels of attention during sport activities (Sarang & Telles, 2006). Beyond physical improvements, yoga fosters emotional wellbeing, builds resilience, and cultivates a positive mental state, all of which are crucial for maintaining consistent athletic performance (Woodyard, 2011). Thus, integrating yoga into training programs can provide a holistic advantage by simultaneously enhancing coordination, mental clarity, and overall health.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to assess the effect of selected yogic practices on two-hand coordination and well-being among male intercollegiate athletes of Kuvempu University during 2022–23.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the purpose of the study, Forty male intercollegiate athletes from Kuvempu University, Shivamogga, were selected and randomly divided into two groups: experimental (n=20) and control (n=20). The experimental group underwent yoga training three days a week (Monday, Wednesday, and Friday) for twelve weeks, while the control group continued with their regular daily activities without additional training.

Two hand coordination was evaluated using a standardized aiming test to assess sensorimotor skills. Participants were seated comfortably and instructed to trace a star-shaped pattern in a clockwise

direction using a stylus, ensuring it remained on the marked path. The time taken to complete the task was recorded as the final score. The apparatus, procured from Jagson Scientific Industries (1964), was used at both the baseline and after twelve weeks of intervention to measure performance changes.

To assess the psychological wellbeing of the participants, the DASS-21 questionnaire (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995) was used. This tool evaluates Depression, Anxiety, and Stress levels. Measurements were taken at the beginning and end of the 12-week training program.

The experimental group participated in a set of 48 yogic practices each week, conducted over three days and repeated consistently for a duration of twelve weeks. During this period, the control group did not engage in any form of yogic practice. The selected yogic practices included Asanas, Pranayama, Suryanamaskar, and Meditation. These were chosen by the researcher based on personal knowledge and in consultation with the supervisor and experts in the field of Yoga. A detailed overview of the practices is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental protocol used for finding the effect of yogic practices on two hand coordination and wellbeing of male intercollegiate level sports persons

Monday	Wednesday	Friday	Timings
Warm up with stretching Exercise	Warm up with stretching Exercise	Warm up with stretching Exercise	3minutes
Omkaara and yoga prayer any mediation posture	Omkaara and yoga prayer any mediation posture	Omkaara and yoga prayer any mediation posture	2minutes
Surya Namskara	Surya Namskara	Surya Namskara	5minutes
Vrikshasana	Veerabhadrasana II	Tadasana	2minutes
Veerabhadrasana I	Garudasana	Utkatasana	2minutes
Treikonasana	Parsva Konasana	Parivruta Konasana	2minutes
Natarajasana	Ardhakati Chakrasana	Vatayanasana	2minutes
Vajrasana	Lolasana	Matysana	2minutes
Ardha Matsyendrasana	Badda Konasana	Supta Virasana	2minutes
Akarna Dhanurasana	Kukutasana	Paschimottasana	2minutes
Gomukasana	Janur Shirshasana	Bhujangasana	2minutes
Sarvangasana	Karnapidasana	Setu Bandasana	2minutes
Halasana	Navasana	Pavana Muktasana	2minutes
Shalabasana	Mayurasana	Dhanurasana	2minutes
Kapalabhati	Kapalabhati	Kapalabhati	2minutes

Naadishodhana	Sadanti	Shitali-Shitkari	2minutes
Trataka- Jatrurataka	Trataka- Jatrurataka	Trataka- Jatrurataka	4minutes
Shavasana	Shavasana	Shavasana	5minutes

Descriptive statistics Mean and Standard Deviations were calculated in the present study to understand the normalcy of data. The ‘t’ ratio was calculated to find out the significance of the difference between the mean during pre and post-test of the experimental as well as control groups. The level of significance for the present investigation was 0.05.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

In order to examine the effect of selected yogic practices on wellbeing of intercollegiate level male sports persons, suitable statistics were employed. The result on descriptive analysis as well as ‘t’ test with regard to differences in wellbeing of control and experimental groups during pre-test is presented in table 1.

Table1. Summary of ‘t’ test for differences in two hand coordination and wellbeing between Control group during pre and post-test situation

Variables		Mean	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Two hand coordination	Control Pre test	2.90±0.86	19	-.961	.349
	Control Post test	3.20±0.91			
Wellbeing	Control Pre test	22.25±3.57	19	-1.086	.291
	Control Post test	23.35±2.28			

From table 1, shows that the control group's two hand coordination and wellbeing scores are normally distributed with consistent standard deviations, indicating sample homogeneity. The ‘t’ test results reveal no significant differences between pre-test and post-test scores. The obtained **t-values (-1.086 for two hand coordination and -0.961 for wellbeing)** are below the **critical value of 2.093** at the 0.05 significance level, confirming that the control group remained stable and was randomly assigned.

The result on descriptive analysis as well as ‘t’ test with regard to differences in two hand coordination and wellbeing of experimental groups during pre and post-test is presented in table 2.

Table 2. Summary of ‘t’ test for differences in two hand coordination and wellbeing between Experimental group during pre and post-test situation

Variables		Mean	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Two hand	Ex, Pre test	3.34±1.11		3.256	.004

coordination	Ex, Post test	2.29±0.73	19		
Wellbeing	Ex, Pre test	23.04±5.74	19	6.563	.000
	Ex, Post test	11.09±6.55			

From table 2, shows that the experimental group's two hand coordination and wellbeing scores during pre- test and post-tests are normally distributed with acceptable consistency. The 't' test results show a significant difference, with t-values of **3.256** for two hand coordination and **6.563** for wellbeing both higher than the **table value of 2.093** at the 0.05 level. This confirms that the groups were homogenous, randomly assigned, and that the experimental group showed clear improvement after the intervention.

DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The two hand coordination and wellbeing of athletes are influenced by various factors related to training and competition. The present study examined the effect of selected yogic practices on these abilities in male intercollegiate athletes. The results showed that twelve weeks of yoga practice led to significant improvement in both two hand coordination and wellbeing. These enhancements are important for better sports performance. The yogic practices used in this study positively impacted on welfare and fine muscle control, which are essential for wellbeing and two hand coordinated movements. Yogic exercises improve eye-hand coordination in male university athletes, likely due to better focus and nervous system function. Similar results were found by Bahrain (2003) and Noorjehan (2012). Most participants were male (68%), and all had more than two years of sports experience. Around 41% reported surfing the internet for 3–5 hours daily. After the intervention, there were significant improvements in stress, sleep, anxiety, mindfulness, psychological rigidity, and experiential avoidance ($p < 0.0001$) (Saraswati et, al 2024).

CONCLUSION

The yogic practices implemented in the present study had a positive impact on two-hand coordination and wellbeing among intercollegiate-level sportspersons. The experimental group showed significant improvement in both areas from pre-test to post-test. In contrast, the control group did not exhibit any significant changes in two hand coordination and wellbeing during the same period.

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